

**DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIALLY ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCIES
IN STUDENTS – AS A SOCIAL PEDAGOGICAL NEED**

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Annotation : in this article, the education of a socially active citizen, a well-rounded young generation with intellectual potential, the formation and development of socially active civic competence in the continuous education system, the upbringing of students and young people as professional professionals in the way of building a civil society, a democratic state, as well as their active civic competence The fact that development is a social and pedagogical necessity is highlighted through the means of pedagogical influence.

Key words: student, competence, reform, socially active citizenship, initiative, social-professionalism, excellence

At the root of the reforms implemented in the education system of our country, raising a socially active, well-rounded young generation is being promoted as the most important problem. In his speech[176] at the 75th session of the UN General Assembly on September 23, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan touched on the issue of youth: "More than half of the population of our country is made up of young people. In our republic, great work is being done to ensure that every young man or woman takes a proper place in society and shows their potential[1]". Youth Parliaments, Youth Affairs Agency are operating in Uzbekistan. In August, the Samarkand international forum dedicated to youth rights was successfully held under the auspices of the United Nations. Taking advantage of this opportunity, I call once again to support the initiative of Uzbekistan on the adoption of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Youth[1]" - his opinion is widely recognized by the world

community. The five important initiatives [2] put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on March 19, 2019 also emphasize the role and importance of the educational institution in educating socially active students and youth. Because in the five most important initiatives that have been put forward, it is necessary to further strengthen the attention to the youth, to involve them in culture, art, physical education and sports, to form the skills of using information technologies in the youth, to promote reading among the youth of our country, to ensure the employment of women [2] "tasks like the development of socially active citizenship competences play an important role in the development of mature youth into a mature generation for the future of the country [2].

On January 24, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan addressed the issue of youth in his address to the Oliy Majlis [3]: "As we aim to make Uzbekistan a developed country, we will achieve this not only through rapid reforms, science and innovation. For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate new generation personnel who will come out as proactive reformers, who think strategically, and who are knowledgeable and qualified." 3].

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of scientific studies on the problem of education were carried out. The scope of pedagogical scientific research has expanded. O. Musurmonova [4; p. 364] conducted research on the problems of developing students' independent thinking and forming the spiritual culture of young people in the educational process.

G. Makhmutov [5; p. 27] expressed on the basis of his scientific views about the laws of teaching and educating students, as well as ways to effectively influence the minds of students in the formation of political and moral qualities, spiritual and moral principles and norms, the norms of behavior of our great ancestors and the culture of behavior .

Mamajonov M. [6;], B. Khodjaev[7; 82 p.] conducted research on the problem of training the young generation with high intellectual, socially active, initiative, moral and moral potential as mature personnel in the framework of the reforms implemented

in our country. O. Jamoldinova [8; p. 51], S. Joraeva[9] touched upon problems such as healthy lifestyle and patriotism among young people, increasing the activity of young people and their spiritual and moral education, social-pedagogical skills in the spirit of national development.

In foreign countries, attention has been paid to the education of the young generation with a socially active citizenship position from the elementary and basic school system. Civic education has become compulsory in England since 2000, based on different educational modules for students. Therefore, the development of active civic competence in young people is considered as an activity aimed at increasing the role of citizens in social life by establishing a civil society[10].

**Pedagogical possibilities of
developing socially active civic
competence in students:**

opportunity to increase the initiative and activity of students while increasing the role of self-governing bodies and civil society institutions in building a democratic society in the country

the role of qualities such as inculcating democratic values (human dignity, generosity, national peace, humanitarianism, freedom, patriotism) in the educational process;

Pedagogical possibilities of forming legal culture and legal consciousness in students, developing knowledge and skills to participate in political processes as an active citizen

opportunities for the development of social-psychological, active citizenship qualities in students through democratic life experience, civic knowledge, skills and qualifications

Figure 1. Pedagogical possibilities of developing socially active citizenship competence

Because the development of socially active civic competence in students can be seen as a condition for building a democratic legal state and the social stability of the society, its sustainable development gradually increasing.

Development of socially active civic competences in students as a socio-pedagogical need to clarify, in our opinion, made it possible to highlight the following considerations:

- The main task of civil society in educating the young generation is to develop a socially active citizen;
- ensuring active social participation of society in all spheres of life by instilling in students the idea of building a democratic state;
- to ensure students' active participation in the construction of civil society by instilling in them the ideals of inter-ethnic harmony, inter-religious tolerance, people's well-being, and the perfect human being;
- preparing students for independent life and developing socio-political and legal literacy in them;
- to increase the development of socially active civic competences in students by showing activity in social projects such as "Mentorship", "Student podium";
- It is possible to develop socially active civic competences of students in higher education institutions through "active participation in the activities of youth union associations, wide involvement in the activities of self-governing bodies".

In conclusion, it should be noted that as a result of the analysis of scientific sources on the development of socially active citizenship competence in students:

- defining the social roles of students as a specially organized lesson and extracurricular activity aimed at studying the rights and obligations of students and mastering (social-cultural (active citizenship) competencies) through the subject

"Uzbekistan Development Strategy: Civil Society";

- the development of socially active civil competences is a condition for building a democratic legal state and increasing the social stability of the society, noting it as a factor of its sustainable development;

- socially active civic competence prepares a person for effective activity in the conditions of a democratic legal state, civil society and market economy;

- today, the socially active civic competence approach is considered a priority, and it was emphasized that its pedagogical and psychological aspects consist in training students who can use their socio-political knowledge in practical activities and in solving a wide range of vital tasks;

- the development of socially active civic competences is an important task, such as explaining to students the set of abilities that allow them to actively, responsibly and effectively implement the entire set of civil rights and obligations in a democratic society, to apply their knowledge and skills in practice.

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